

SEARCH FOR NEW INSECTICIDES. PART IV

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5-Chloro-(I), 3:5-dichloro-(II), 4-methyl-5-chloro-(III) and 5-*www*-tetrachloro-(IV) 2-hydroxyacetophenones have been prepared by Fries reaction. 3-Chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (V) and () have been obtained by the Friedel-Crafts reaction between acetyl chloride and *o*- and *p*-chlorophenols respectively, and subsequent hydrolysis of the acetates formed. Methyl, ethyl and propyl ethers (I), (II), (III) and (V) have been prepared.

In extension of our previous work on this subject (this *Juornal*, 1948, 25, 277 ; 1949, 26 243, 287) we have now synthesised a number of halogen-substituted hydroxyacetophenone and their alkyl ethers with a view to studying them for their possible insecticidal action. These compounds are expected to possess good insecticidal action as they contain in their molecule the residues of different inhalation narcotics (viz., CCl_3 , COCH_3 , COCCl_3 , OCH_3 etc.) attached to the poisonous chlorobenzene ring ; that this type of combination is essential for a good contact insecticide is already known (Busvine, *Nature*, 1935, 156, 169). Five hydroxyketones viz., 5-chloro-(I), 3:5-dichloro- (II), 4-methyl-5-chloro- (III), 5-*www*-tetrachloro-(IV) and 3-chloro- (V) 2-hydroxy-acetophenones have been prepared ; (I), (II), (III) and (V) have been subsequently converted into their methyl, ethyl and propyl ethers. It may be mentioned that a number of alkyl halogen phenols have already been shown to possess good bactericidal properties (Klarman, Shternov and Gates, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 2576).

(I), (II), (III) and (V) have been prepared by the Fries rearrangement of the corresponding acetates. The first three of these compounds have been previously obtained by this method by several authors (Wittig, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 88, 1270 ; *Annalen*, 1926, 446, 155; Karre *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1930, 13, 1308 ; Klarman *et al.*, *loc. cit.* Chien and Yin, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 7, 40 ; Rosenmund and Schnurr, *Annalen*, 1928, 460, 56). *o*-Chlorophenyl acetate could not be rearranged even on heating at 140° for 8 hours with 1½ mole of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

The Friedel-Crafts reaction between acetyl chloride and *p*- and *o*- chlorophenols in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride resulted in a formation of the acetates of 5-chloro and 3-chloro-2-hydroxy-acetophenones respectively in very good yields (cf. Nencki and Stoeber, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1771 ; Claus, *Chem. Zentr.* 1898, II, 158; these authors have carried out the above reaction in presence of anhydrous ferric chloride, and obtained 5-chloro-2-hydroxy- and 3-chloro-4-hydroxy- acetophenones in the case of *p*- and *o*- chlorophenols respectively). These acetates yielded the corresponding phenols on hydrolysis with alkali

The methyl, ethyl and propyl ethers of (I), (II), (III) and (V) were obtained in good yields (60-90%) by using dimethyl sulphate, ethyl iodide and propyl bromide respectively. Methyl ethers of 2-hydroxy-5-chloro- and 2-hydroxy-4-methyl-5-chloro- acetophenones have been previously described, the former having been obtained by the action of acetyl chloride on

methyl ether of *p*-chlorophenol in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride (Wittig, *Ber.*, 1924, **57**, 93) or by methylation of the corresponding hydroxy compound with methyl iodide (Chakravarti and Dutta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **17**, 66), and the latter by the methylation of 2-hydroxy-5-chloro-4-methylacetophenone by dimethyl sulphate (Wittig, *Annalen*, 1926, **446**, 155).

All the *o*-hydroxyacetophenones prepared, gave the Pyman's test (Gulthard, Marshall and Pyman, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280) for *o*-hydroxy- ketones and also gave intense violet coloration with 1% ferric chloride. The ethers obtained are insoluble in water, dilute alkali or acids, but dissolve in all common organic solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

Acetates of the Halogen-substituted Phenols.—*p*-Chlorophenyl acetate (b.p. 127°/22mm.) was obtained from *p*-chlorophenol (32.1 g.), acetic anhydride (24 c.c.) and anhydrous sodium acetate (10 g.) by the method of Wohleben (*Ber.*, 1910, **43**, 4372; b.p. 108°/12.5 mm.) in nearly theoretical yield. The acetate of 3-methyl-4-chlorophenol (b.p. 143°-145°/17-18 mm.) was similarly prepared from the phenol (20g.), acetic anhydride (22 c.c.) and sodium acetate (8 g.) in approximately theoretical yield (Nathan Sulzberger, A.P. 149860; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1927, II, 1893, who used concentrated sulphuric acid as the dehydrating agent, reports b.p. 241°-243°). 2:4-Dichlorophenyl acetate (b.p. 135°-137°/18-19 mm.) was obtained by the method of Fischer (*Ann. Spl.* 7, 184, b.p. 244°-245°; Chien and Yin, *loc. cit.*, give b.p. 167°-168°/80mm.) from 32.6 g. of the phenol and 30 g. of acetyl chloride by heating to 50-60° for about 2 hours, the yield being 78.3% of theory. In all the above cases, the acetate was isolated by extraction with ether and distillation in vacuum, after removal of the ether from the dried ethereal extract.

The trichloroacetate of *p*-chlorophenol (b.p. 115°/20mm.) was prepared by the method described by us previously (this *Journal*, 1948, **25**, 280).

Fries Rearrangement of the Acetates of the Halogen-substituted Phenols.—The acetate (1*M*) and anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 *M* approx.) were taken in a 500 c.c. pyrex flask fitted with a reflux condenser, and the contents of the flask gradually heated, first over a water-bath and then in an oil-bath, the temperature being raised to 125° during the course of an hour and maintained between 125° and 130° for about 3 hours (excepting in the case of 3-methyl-4-chlorophenylacetate, which required only 1 hour at this temperature to rearrange). The contents of the flask were then cooled, treated with ice and hydrochloric acid and left overnight for the decomposition to be complete. The oil separating (a semi-solid mass in some cases) was extracted with ether and the ethereal extract washed, dried and filtered. On removal of the ether from the filtrate and distillation of the residual liquid in vacuum, the *ortho*-hydroxyacetophenone corresponding to the acetate used, was obtained. The ketones thus prepared are described in Table I.

Acetates of 5-Chloro- and 3-Chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenones.—These compounds were obtained by the action of acetyl chloride on *p*- and *o*-chlorophenols respectively, in presence of anhydrous aluminium chloride as described below.

The *p*- or *o*-chlorophenol was covered with petrol-ether (50-75 c.c.) in a 250 c.c. flask, cooled in ice, and aluminium chloride ($1\frac{1}{2}$ -2 moles) added. The flask was then attached to a reflux condenser and acetyl chloride (1-2 moles) added dropwise from the top of the condenser. After the brisk reaction had subsided (which takes about one hour), the contents of the flask were refluxed over a water-bath for 2 hours and left overnight. On distilling off the petrol ether from the mixture and decomposing the residue with dilute hydrochloric acid as usual, a dark coloured oil was obtained, which was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was well washed with water, dried over calcium chloride, filtered and the ether removed. The acetate of the chloro-*o*-hydroxyacetophenone corresponding to the chlorophenol used, was obtained on distilling the residual liquid in vacuum.

The acetate of 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone was thus obtained as a colorless liquid, b.p. 144° - 146° /1mm., from *p*-chlorophenol (13 g.), acetyl chloride (14g.) and aluminium chloride (23 g.) (Wittig, *Annalen*, 1926, **446**, 155, who obtained this compound from 2-acetyl-4-chlorophenol, acetyl chloride and calcium chloride, gave b.p. 156° - 157° /14mm.), yield 17g. (79% of theory). (Found : C, 56.13 ; H, 4.11 ; Cl, 16.67. Calc. for $C_{10}H_9O_3Cl$: C, 56.57 ; H, 4.23 ; Cl, 16.75 per cent).

The acetate of 3-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone was similarly obtained from *o*-chlorophenol (26 g.), acetyl chloride (28 g.) and aluminium chloride (46 g.), as a colorless liquid, b.p. 151° - 154° /1mm., yield 35.6 g. (82.8% of theory). (Found : C, 56.14 ; H, 4.09 ; Cl, 16.27. $C_{10}H_9O_3Cl$ requires C, 56.47 ; H, 4.23 ; Cl, 16.75 per cent).

5-Chloro- and 3-Chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenones (by hydrolysis of the acetates).—The acetates, described above, yielded the free phenols on hydrolysing with 20% caustic potash solution (4 c.c. for every g. of the acetate) for half an hour. The resulting solution was cooled and acidified with hydrochloric acid, and the oil that separated out, was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed, dried over calcium chloride, filtered and the ether removed from the filtrate. The chlorohydroxyacetophenone was obtained on distilling the residual liquid in vacuum.

The acetate of 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone, thus on hydrolysis, yielded 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone, b.p. 126° - 128° /28mm. (described elsewhere also in this paper), yield 90.7% of theory. (Found : C, 56.02 ; H, 3.87 ; Cl, 20.91. Calc. for $C_9H_7O_2Cl$: C, 56.30 ; H, 4.11 ; Cl, 20.82 per cent).

3-Chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (b.p. 87 - 89° /1 mm.) was similarly obtained from the corresponding acetate as a colorless liquid, yield 93.5% of theory. (Found : C, 56.17 ; H, 4.07 ; Cl, 20.93. $C_9H_7O_2Cl$ requires C, 56.30 ; H, 4.11 ; Cl, 20.82 per cent).

Alkyl Ethers of Substituted Hydroxyacetophenones.—The methyl ethers were prepared from the hydroxy compound (4-5 g.), 10% caustic soda solution (containing approximately $1\frac{1}{2}$ to 2 times the requisite amount of alkali) and dimethyl sulphate ($1\frac{1}{2}$ to 2 times the requisite amount) by the usual method. The reagents were heated for 5 hours under continuous stirring and then left overnight. The oil separating after dilution with water was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed and dried and the ether removed as usual. The methyl ether was obtained on distilling the residual liquid in vacuum.

TABLE I

Ketone, base.	Obtained from see- AlCl ₃ .	B.p.	Yield (% of theory).	Properties of the liquid.	Formula	Found (%)			Calc. (%)			
						C.	H.	Cl.	C.	H.	Cl.	
I	35 g.	54.5 g.	107-109°/12 mm.	51.4	Colorless, solidifying on chilling in ice.	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ Cl	56.10	3.93	20.61	56.30	4.11	20.82
II	27	34.5	132°-134°/18	70.4	Colorless, solidifying to white crystals on cooling in ice.	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ Cl	46.63	2.67	34.41	46.83	2.92	34.63
III	22	32	140°-142°/21	83.6	Colorless, solidifying to white crystals on cooling in ice.	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ Cl	58.14	4.63	19.43	58.53	4.88	19.24
IV	18	18	129°-32°/44	26	Brilliant yellow liquid, turning brown in a few weeks	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ Cl	34.81	1.59	51.61	35.04	1.46	51.82

I = 5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (Klarman, Shternon and Gates, *loc. cit.*, give b.p. 97.99°/2 mm.).
 II = 3:6-dichloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (Chen and Yin, *loc. cit.*, give m. p. 95-96°).
 III = 4-methyl-5-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone (Rosenmund and Schnorr, *loc. cit.*, give b. p. 137°/15 mm.).
 IV = 5-*o*-tert-butyl-2-hydroxyacetophenone.

TABLE II

Name.	B.p.	Yield (%) of theory).	Properties of the liquid.	Formula.	Found (%)			Calculated (%)		
					C.	H.	Cl.	C.	H.	Cl.
Methyl ether of I ^a	108°/2 mm.	79.2	Colorless, solidifying on cooling in ice.	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ Cl	58.17	4.70	19.01	58.53	4.88	19.24
Ethyl ether of I	142°/1.	63.2	Colorless	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	60.24	5.51	18.46	60.45	5.54	17.88
Propyl ether of I	110-12°/1	84.4	"	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ Cl	61.93	6.07	16.36	62.12	6.11	16.70
Methyl ether of II	148°/43	91.4	"	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ Cl ₂	48.89	3.52	32.40	49.31	3.61	32.42
Ethyl ether of II	175°/2	64.7	"	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ O ₂ Cl ₂	51.81	4.19	30.26	51.50	4.29	30.47
Propyl ether of II	142°/2	51.5	"	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	53.41	4.67	29.40	53.44	4.86	29.15
Methyl ether of III ^t	111°/0.5	75.4	Colorless, solidifying on cooling in ice.	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	60.19	5.39	17.79	60.45	5.54	17.88
Ethyl ether of III	160°/4	70.0	Pale yellow	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ Cl	61.91	6.01	16.56	62.12	6.11	16.70
Propyl ether of III	158°/2	55.0	Pale yellow	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ Cl	63.39	6.41	15.43	63.62	6.62	15.67
Methyl ether of V	88°/1	68.6	Colorless	C ₉ H ₇ O ₂ Cl	58.09	4.67	19.42	58.53	4.88	19.24
Ethyl ether of V	91-93°/1	72.1	Colorless, turning red and then brown on keeping.	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ O ₂ Cl	60.24	5.37	18.06	60.45	5.54	17.88
Propyl ether of V	108-10/1	47.0	Colorless.	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ Cl	62.07	5.91	16.53	62.12	6.11	16.70

I-III, as referred to in Table I.

V = 3-chloro-2-hydroxyacetophenone.

^a. Wittig, *Ber.*, 1924, 57, 93, gives m.p. 29-30°, Chakravarty and Datta, *loc. cit.*, give b.p. 136°/6 mm.

^t. Wittig, *Annalen*, 1926, 446, 155, gives m.p. 79-80°.

The *ethyl and propyl ethers* were prepared from 5-4 g. of the phenol, sodium ethoxide and alkyl halide ($1\frac{1}{2}$ to 2 times the calculated amount of each of these) (ethyl iodide and propyl bromide were used for the ethyl and propyl ethers respectively) in the usual way. The reagents were refluxed for 3 hours. After removal of the excess of alcohol by distillation, the residue was cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed, dried, ether removed and the residual liquid distilled in vacuum when the ether corresponding to the phenol and the alkyl halide used was obtained.

The ethers that have thus been prepared are described in Table II.

The insecticidal action of the compounds, described in this paper, is under investigation.

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